

Silver plasmons sensitized photocatalytic activity of bismuth ferrite (BiFeO₃) nanoparticles

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Abstract : Silver (Ag) plasmons sensitized bismuth ferrite (BiFeO₃-BFO) hybrid nanoparticles were synthesized by sol-gel combined chemical reduction method. The synthesized Ag : BFO nano-hybrids was studied for their photocatalytic ability to degrade organic pollutant such as methylene blue under the sunlight exposure. The formation of Ag and BFO phase was confirmed by the X-ray diffraction studies. The high resolution transmission electron micrographs showed that the Ag NPs were well deposited on the surface of BFO particles. UV-Visible absorption studies revealed that the sensitization of BFO with nanoscale Ag has significantly enhanced its visible light absorption and subsequent photocatalytic activities. The results reported here suggest that the surface plasmon resonance (SPR), which is manifested on the nanoscale silver, enhanced the quantum yield of photo-generated electron-transfer processes by boosting up the charge separation in BFO and by promoting the shuttle electrons to the interface of catalyst-dye and thereby effectively degraded the dye molecules.

Keywords : Multiferroics, photocatalyst, surface plasmon resonance, plasmonic sensitization.

Introduction

The current scenario of increasing demand for energy production and environment cleaning has propelled the search for new multifunctional materials in these fields. Photocatalytic materials are expected to be one of such multifunctional materials that can be used to produce energy such as hydrogen and to clean the environment via degrading the organic pollutants in water, etc.¹. Therefore, it is highly essential to develop environment friendly, cost-effective and sunlight driven photocatalytic materials in particular is of prime significance. Bismuth ferrite (BiFeO₃/BFO) is a well established multiferroic material that shows simultaneous magnetic and ferroelectric property at room temperature which also possesses high Neel (643 K) and Curie transition (1100 K) temperatures². Recently, BFO is also being studied for their photocatalytic property owing to its narrow band gap (~2.2 eV) on its ability to degrade various organic pollutants³. Accordingly BFO has been synthesized by controlling its morphological and compositional parameters towards

enhancing its visible light driven photocatalytic properties⁴. The photocatalysts sensitized with noble metals (i.e. Ag, Au, Pt) are found to be very receptive to the visible light, especially the sunlight. This is because of that the nanoscale noble metals effectively absorb visible light owing to their Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR) properties. They also work as electron trapping and active reaction centres. In plasmonic metals, the conduction electrons oscillate when they hit by oscillating electric field of the incident light, and SPR occurs when the frequency of these oscillating electrons are in resonance with frequency of the incident light⁵. The SPR is profoundly useful because it provides light absorption in visible, near infrared (IR) and IR region⁶. Therefore sensitizing photocatalysts with such nanoscale noble metals can be expected to enhance the photocatalytic properties under sunlight. Accordingly, our work reports the synthesis of silver (Ag) plasmon sensitized BFO nanoparticles and their sunlight driven photocatalytic property towards the degradation of organic pollutant such as methylene blue (MB).

Experimental

BFO nanoparticles were synthesized by sol-gel method. In the typical procedure, 0.1 M of bismuth nitrate and iron nitrate precursors were taken and dissolved in 25 ml of de-ionized water. To this, 0.2 M of citric acid was added followed by the addition of 2 ml of nitric acid (HNO₃) to obtain a homogeneous solution. Then, the solution was heated to ~80 °C and dried to powder. Finally, the dried powder was annealed at 650 °C for 3 h to obtain the BiFeO₃ phase. The chemical reduction method was adopted to sensitize the synthesized BFO with Ag nanoparticles (Ag NPs). The synthesized BFO NPs and silver nitrate precursor was taken in 1 : 0.25, 1 : 0.5, 1 : 0.75 and 1 : 1 ratio and dissolved in the ethanol-water mixture solution and stirred well for 2 h. Then silver nitrate was reduced to silver NPs on the surface of BFO by adding 100 ml of 0.1 M sodium borohydride (NaBH₄) solution to the above mixture.

For the photocatalytic studies, initially, 10 mg MB was dissolved in 1 litre of de-ionized water to prepare the MB solution. Accordingly, 50 mg of pure and Ag : BFO (1 : 0.25, 1 : 0.5, 1 : 0.75, 1 : 1 ratio) catalysts were taken separately and added to 100 ml of MB solution taken from the stock solution. Then, the catalyst-dye solution was kept under the irradiation of sun light, and degradation of dye was monitored by using UV-Visible

absorption spectroscopy every 30 min. All the synthesized Ag sensitized BFO hybrid NPs were characterized for their structural, morphological, optical and photocatalytic properties by X-ray diffraction (XRD), high resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) and UV-Visible spectroscopy techniques respectively.

Results and discussion

Fig. 1(a) shows the XRD pattern of BFO, Ag and Ag sensitized BFO nanoparticles (Ag : BFO, at 1 : 0.25, 1 : 0.5, 1 : 0.57 and 1 : 1 ratio). The XRD pattern of BFO is well matched with JCPDS Card No. 20-0169 and showed that the BFO possessed rhombohedrally distorted perovskite crystal structure with space group R3c.

The diffraction peaks corresponding to Ag clearly revealed that the BFO was well sensitized with high crystalline Ag nanoparticles. However, the XRD pattern of Ag : BFO showed impurity phases such as Ag₂O and Bi₂Fe₄O₉ at the higher concentration Ag in the BFO host. This could be due to deposition of Ag NPs on the surface of BFO modified its surface chemistry and leading to the formation of such Bi₂Fe₄O₉ and Ag₂O phases.

The HRTEM images of the Ag sensitized BFO nanoparticles are shown in Fig. 1(b)-(e) and it revealed that the silver NPs were well attached on the surface of BFO. The morphology of BFO and Ag NPs was found to

Fig. 1. (a) XRD pattern of pure BFO, Ag and Ag : BFO NPs and HRTEM micrograph of Ag : BFO at the ratio of (b) 0.25 : 1, (c) 0.5 : 1, (d) 0.75 : 1 and (e) 1 : 1.

Fig. 2. (a) UV-Visible absorption spectra and (b) photocatalytic degradation efficiency of pure and Ag : BFO NPs and its photocatalytic mechanism (insert image).

be irregular with size around 100 nm and spherical in shape with size around 25 nm, respectively. The concentration of Ag NPs was found to be increased with increasing concentration of silver nitrate precursor.

Fig. 2(a) shows the UV-Visible absorption spectra of pure and Ag sensitized BFO hybrids. Compared to pure BFO, the absorption peak of Ag sensitized BFO became wider and moved towards the higher wavelengths, which clearly revealed that they would be more receptive to the visible light and possibly upto the near IR region.

Fig. 2(b) presents the comparative degradation (C/C_0) graph of pure and Ag : BFO NPs. It was found that the degradation efficiency of Ag : BFO was increasing with increasing concentration of Ag. This could be due to the enhancement in the collective SPR effect in Ag : BFO with increasing concentration of Ag. The mechanism of the observed enhancement in the photocatalytic degradation of Ag : BFO essentially involves the transfer of photo-induced electrons from BFO to Ag and further promotion of charge carriers to the BFO-dye interface as depicted in the insert of Fig. 2(b).

In this Ag : BFO hybrid structure, the Fermi level of Ag NPs occurs between the valence band (VB) and conduction band (CB) of BFO when a contact was established between Ag and BFO. Consequently, the formation and separation of electrons-holes (e^-/h^+) carriers in BFO were get enhanced upon the impingement of the incident sunlight⁷. Further, the recombination rate of these

excited e^-/h^+ pairs was effectively reduced due to their entrapment of the electrons on the surface of BFO. Such entrapment process is likely made the BFO as a charge-polarized semiconductor⁸. Subsequently, these entrapped carriers were promoted to the BFO-dye interface and thereby they performed reduction and oxidation reactions and lead to an effective degradation of the MB dye molecules⁸.

Conclusion

Silver nanoparticles sensitized bismuth ferrite nanoscale plasmonic photocatalyst was developed by combining sol-gel and chemical reduction methods. The XRD pattern of the synthesized Ag : BFO hybrids confirmed the formation of well crystalline silver and bismuth ferrite (BiFeO_3) phases. The HRTEM micrographs showed that the Ag NPs were well attached on the surface of BFO. It was also observed that the BFO and Ag possessed aggregated-irregular and spherical morphology with size around 100 and 25 nm, respectively. The visible light absorption characteristics and the photocatalytic efficiency of Ag : BFO was found to be increased with increasing concentration of Ag on BFO. It was suggested that the increasing photocatalytic activity of Ag : BFO was due to the collective SPR effect of Ag NPs. In which, the SPR of Ag NPs led to a stronger absorption of visible light and enhanced the production of charge carries in BFO. Further, the Ag NPs also trapped the excited electrons of BFO in its conduction band and subsequently reduced the recombina-

tion possibilities of the charge carriers. Thereby, these charge carriers were effortlessly promoted to the BFO-dye interface and produced more number of redox species by interacting with surrounded medium and degraded the dye molecules very efficiently.

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